

THE ROLE OF TOUR OPERATORS IN THE SYSTEM OF ECONOMIC RELATIONS

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ABSTRACT

According to the World Travel & Tourism Council, the contribution of the tourism industry to the world economy in 2022 will be 8.6 trillion dollars⁵⁴, which is only 6.4% behind the level before the pandemic. Of course, the activity of the tour operator also has its own contribution, and it has its place in tourism as an economic lever.

Keywords: Tour, tour operator, tour agency, tour operator activity, tourist services, customer, tourism industry,

According to the decision⁵⁵ of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 433 of July 10, 2020: "Regulation on the procedure for providing tour operator and travel agency services": "Tour operator activity - formation, promotion and promotion of tourist products business activity carried out by a legal entity in connection with the realization" is defined.

Organizations engaged in the preparation and sale of tours are called tourist and excursion organizations. In practice, they can be named differently: tour operator, travel agencies, travel agency, travel firm, etc., but according to the type of business in the tourism market, they can be divided into travel agencies and tour operators. The terms "tour agency" and "tour operator" define the direction of business activity of a tourist firm or company.

The tourist product is formed from the services of enterprises that provide services to people in recreation and travel. These are transport companies, hotels, restaurants, cafes, tour companies, museums and exhibitions, amusement parks, leisure and entertainment enterprises, shows, cinema, video business, gambling events and institutions, sports and resort organizations.

Tour operators are engaged in the formation of a complete set of tourist products, that is, a set of services called "tour". A tour operator (in some countries it is called a

⁵⁴ <https://wtcc.org/Portals/0/Documents/Reports/2022/EIR2022-Global%20Trends.pdf>

⁵⁵ O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 10.07.2020 yildagi «O'zbekiston Respublikasida turizm sohasini tiklash va rivojlantirish uchun qulay shart-sharoitlarni yaratish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida»gi 433-son qarori

tour organizer) produces differentiated tourism products from service components according to the needs and wishes of customers⁵⁶.

The tour operator develops tourist routes, fills them with services through interaction with service providers, ensures the operation of tours and the provision of services, prepares advertising and informational publications for their tours, calculates prices for tours, transfers the tours to the travel agency. then sell to tourists.

The primary market function of these organizations is to connect service providers with tourism customers, sometimes in a time and geographically dispersed manner. In these economic relations, it is important to choose the right service providers based on professional knowledge of the tourism market, business, features and levers of its development and management.

Travel agencies and tour operators can have different forms of ownership. They can be private, state, joint-stock companies - the essence of business activity and their market functions do not change.

The main task of both the travel agent and the tour operator in the market is to have a stable position in the tourism market and to get stable profits. Based on the differentiation of the tourism market, it is necessary to find its place, the consumer segment. The history of the tourism network is considered one of the types of human activity that began long before the emergence of a cultural society. In every historical period, there were elements of human activity that belong to the category of tourism. The importance of the activity of tour operators in the life of people, regions, countries and international life cannot be ignored. Currently, the activity of tour operators in the market of tourist services is one of the strong networks that include various forms of services to the people in the field of tourism and satisfy their needs.

A tour operator is an active participant of the tourism market who organizes tours according to contracts with service providers and is an active participant of the tourism market, directly participating in the planning, production, advertising and sale of tourist products for commercial purposes. A tour operator produces tourist products according to the needs and wishes of customers, plays a special role in the tourism industry, that is, receives tourist services, forms a tourist product and sells it directly or through intermediaries (tour agents) for profit.

Authors of many textbooks and training manuals in the field of tourism and services have given their own interpretation to the term tour operator. The author of the textbook "Organization of Tourism" A.P. According to Durovich, the activity of a tour operator is the activity of forming, advertising and selling a tourist product to consumers directly and through travel agents.

⁵⁶ Гостиничный и туристский бизнес. под ред. проф. Чудновского А.Д. - М.: Ассоциация авторов и издателей «Тандем». Изд - во «ЭКМОС», 2003 г. - 352

The tour operator provides tourists with a diverse selection of tourist services and at the same time simplifies the ordering of services by taking over these functions in other cities and districts. R.I. Sukhov, the author of the textbook "Organization of Travel Agency Work" believes that the content of the law can be reasonably criticized, but in his manual he uses official terms⁵⁷.

The main task of the tour operator is to create a tour that provides the appropriate service program, and this product is the main tourist product of the tour operator that is released to the market and sold through the agency network. Creating an attractive tourist product is the first and most important task of a tour operator. This field of activity of tourist enterprises is directly related to production processes. The company's product policy requires mutually agreed decisions on production and sales, as well as the assortment of types, service programs, and the amount of tourist products.

Based on the above, the duties of the tour operator can be defined as follows:

1. To study the needs of potential tourists for tours and tourist programs;
2. Developing promising service programs, tours and testing them on the market in order to determine their suitability to the needs of tourists;
3. Mutual cooperation with the following suppliers providing tour services on the basis of the contract:
 - hotels - providing accommodation to tourists;
 - catering establishments - providing tourists with food;
 - transport enterprises, firms and companies - providing transport services to tourists;
 - tourist companies, museums, exhibition halls, parks and other institutions - providing excursion services to tourists.
4. Calculating the price of a tour, transtour and determining the price taking into account the market situation. Establishing tariffs and prices for their services on the embodiment of different content, category and other types;
5. Providing tourists traveling along tour routes with all necessary advertising and souvenir materials, special equipment and inventory;
6. Training, selection and route assignment of personnel performing communication functions with tourists, coordination and control of implementation of service programs (guides, instructors, animators, methodists, etc.);
7. Advertising and information activities to promote its tourist product to consumers;
8. Promotion and sale of tourist tours to consumers through the system of travel agencies;

⁵⁷ Санникова, И.Н. Современное состояние международного туризма в мировой экономике / И.Н. Санникова // Вестник магистратуры. – 2017. - № 4. – С. 64-65.

9. Monitoring the reliability and quality of the service;

10. To be in constant operational contact with tourists during the service, to solve the arising problems.

Currently, there are 121 tour companies operating in Bukhara region, and they have been operating at a much more significant level since the pandemic.

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